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Revival of recombinant IL-2 therapy – approaches from the past until today

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ABSTRACT

Interleukin-2 (IL-2) was one of the first cytokines discovered and its central role in T cell function soon led to the notion that the cytokine could specifically activate immune cells to combat cancer cells. Recombinant human IL-2 (reclL-2) belonged to the first anti-cancer immunotherapeutics that received marketing authorization and while it mediated anti-tumor effects in some cancer entities, treatment was associated with severe and systemic side effects. ReclL-2 holds an exceptional therapeutic potential, which can either lead to stimulation of the immune system – favorable during cancer treatment – or immunosuppression – used for treatment of inflammatory diseases such as autoimmunity. Due to these pleiotropic immune effects, reclL-2 therapy is still a hot topic in research and modified reclL-2 drug candidates show ameliorated efficacy and safety in pre-clinical and clinical studies. The Immune Safety Avatar (imSAVAR) consortium aims to systemically assess mechanisms leading to adverse events provoked by reclL-2 immunotherapy as a use case in order to aid safety evaluation of future reclL-2-based therapies. Here, we summarize the historical use of reclL-2 therapy, associated side effects, and describe the molecular basis of the dual role of IL-2. Finally, an overview of new reclL-2 compounds and delivery systems, which are currently being developed, will be given, highlighting a possible comeback of reclL-2 therapy.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Interleukin-2 from discovery to therapy

In 1976, interleukin-2 (IL-2) had been discovered as a growth factor in conditioned supernatants of mitogen-activated lymphocyte cultures selectively supporting the proliferation and survival of T-cells within human bone marrow cultures (Morgan et al. 1976). During this time, cellular immunity had been shown to play a critical role in tissue rejection, which in turn was

identified as a treatment strategy of cancer. Application of Bacille Calmette-Guérin or *Cryptosporidium parvum* were early approaches that aimed at tumor treatment via nonspecific immune stimulation but remained unsuccessful (Rosenberg 1988). Hence, IL-2, at that time called “T-cell growth factor,” with the potential to kill tumor cells by selectively activating immune cells became a hot candidate to be used in anti-tumor immunotherapy. Along with the isolation of the IL-2 cDNA

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clone in 1983, enabling the production of recombinant human IL-2 (recIL-2), this was seen as a major breakthrough regarding the treatment of cancer diseases (Taniguchi et al. 1983; Rosenberg 1988).

Intensive studies by Rosenberg and colleagues showed that besides the activation of cytotoxic T-lymphocytes and natural killer (NK) cells, which are key players in eliminating malignant cells, another subset of “tumor-killers” can be generated upon IL-2-treatment of murine splenocytes or human peripheral blood cells *in vitro* (Lotze et al. 1981; Grimm et al. 1982). These so-called lymphokine-activated killer (LAK) cells were described as part of a unique cytotoxic effector system with the potential to eliminate NK cell-resistant solid tumors. Their ability to combat syngeneic and autologous tumor cells and their potential to reduce the production of metastases has been demonstrated in murine models and in the human system including co-culture analyses with cells from cancer patients (Lotze et al. 1981; Grimm et al. 1982; Talmadge et al. 1987; Rosenberg 1988). The idea of treating patients by adoptively transferring LAK cells with or without additional recIL-2 was amended after the finding that high-dose recIL-2 can induce comparable effects *in vivo* so that the transfer of LAK cells appeared unnecessary. This saved resources since high amounts of recIL-2 are needed to generate LAK cells and moreover, provided a less invasive treatment for patients. With this, clinical trials started focusing on high-dose recIL-2 therapy of patients suffering from metastatic renal cell carcinoma or metastatic melanoma. Fyfe et al. and Atkins et al. summarized clinical trial data from those patient groups (255 patients with renal cell carcinoma and 270 patients with metastatic melanoma) over 5-7 years in the 1980s and 1990s (Fyfe et al. 1995; Atkins et al. 1999). Due to the short half-life, a high-dose of 600 000 or 720 000 IU/kg recIL-2 was infused intravenously (iv), every 8 h for 14 consecutive doses over 5 days, and 5-9 days of rest before starting another cycle. A repetition of the courses was offered in stable or responding patients after 6 or 12 weeks. The renal cell carcinoma and metastatic melanoma patient groups revealed overall response rates of 14% and 16% and median response durations of 20.3 and 8.9 months, respectively. Regression of tumors was observed at different sites in the body such as lymph nodes, lung, and liver. Metastatic melanoma patients responding for more than 30 months were free of disease progression. Indeed, not only response rates and durability but also observed toxicities (described below) were comparable for both patient groups and apparently reversible. However, the severity of toxic effects is underlined by the fact that up to 4% of patients died from adverse events. On the other hand, low response rates are associated with a massive expansion of regulatory T-cells (T_{regs}) which have a higher affinity toward IL-2 as compared to T-effector cells (T_{effs}) (described in detail below), preventing anti-tumor effects (Yao et al. 2012; Sim et al. 2014).

The recIL-2 aldesleukin, marketed as Proleukin[®], was approved by the FDA for the treatment of metastatic renal cell carcinoma and metastatic melanoma in 1992 and 1998, respectively. Currently, lower doses of recIL-2 are also used (mostly subcutaneously [sc]) in a variety of indications such as HIV-infection, tuberculosis, but also autoimmune diseases and conditions with inflammatory backgrounds such as systemic lupus erythematosus (Mahmoudpour et al. 2019; Rosenzweig et al. 2019; Graßhoff et al. 2021). Meanwhile, second generation recIL-2 constructs aiming at a better tolerability whilst maintaining efficacy are under clinical investigation and are described more closely below. Thus, recIL-2 treatment up to now comes in different doses, application routes, and novel recIL-2 products.

The dual role of IL-2 in immune regulation

More than 45 years after its discovery, the central role of IL-2 in T-cell development and function was further established. Knockout mouse models have added to the knowledge regarding the importance of IL-2 for the development of T_{reg} cells, preventing autoimmunity (reviewed by Malek and Bayer, 2004). IL-2 was shown to be a key survival factor for T_{reg} cells and mediates their homeostasis and suppressive capacity (Bensinger et al. 2004; Fontenot et al. 2005; Barron et al. 2010). On the other hand, IL-2 can expand T_{effs} and amplify antigen-specific responses, thereby mediating immunostimulation. Specifically, IL-2 can assist in $CD4^+$ T-cell proliferation and support differentiation of naïve $CD4^+$ T-cells into T-helper type (T_H)-2 cells (Cote-Sierra et al. 2004), T_H9 cells (Liao et al. 2014), and prevent their development into T_H17 cells (Laurence et al. 2007). In line with its effects on $CD4^+$ T-cell differentiation, IL-2 can support terminal differentiation of $CD8^+$ T-cells. Furthermore, upon IL-2 stimulation, $\gamma\delta$ T-cells can acquire interferon- γ production and cytolytic activity. In addition, IL-2 induces proliferation of and cytokine production by NK and group 2 innate lymphoid cells (Kehrl et al. 1988; Roediger et al. 2013) and increases the cytotoxic activity of NK cells (Kehrl et al. 1988). Physiologic sources of IL-2 mainly include activated $CD4^+$ T-cells, or, to a lesser extent, activated $CD8^+$ T-cells, on which IL-2 acts in an autocrine and paracrine manner. Furthermore, activated cells of the innate immune system are known to produce IL-2 including dendritic cells (Granucci et al. 2001), NK cells (Sanctis et al. 1997), or mast cells (Hershko et al. 2011).

After secretion or during recIL-2 therapy, IL-2 can bind to cells expressing the IL-2 receptor (IL-2R), which is composed of up to three subunits, IL-2R α (CD25), IL-2R β (CD122), and IL-2R γ (CD132). Of the three receptor subunits, only IL-2R α is specific for IL-2. IL-2R β is shared by IL-15 (Giri et al. 1994) and IL-2R γ , also termed the common gamma chain, is shared by IL-4 (Kondo et al. 1993), IL-7 (Noguchi et al. 1993), IL-9 (Kimura et al. 1995), IL-15 (Giri et al. 1994), and IL-21 (Asao et al. 2001). The dual role of IL-2 signaling either leading to activation of the immune system or to immunosuppression can in part be accounted for by differential expression of IL-2R subunits on different cell subsets. Depending on the composition of their receptor subunits, different affinities to IL-2 can be achieved. While IL-2R γ alone does not interact with IL-2, IL-2R β can bind IL-2 with low-affinity and subsequently interact with IL-2R γ to form the intermediate-affinity IL-2R ($K_d \sim 1$ nM). IL-2R α alone is the low-affinity IL-2R ($K_d \sim 10$ nM) and formation of the high-affinity trimeric IL-2R ($K_d \sim 10$ pM) is induced by binding of IL-2 to IL-2R α , resulting in a conformational change in the cytokine. Subsequently, the affinity of IL-2 for IL-2R β is increased and interaction with IL-2R γ forms the functional high-affinity IL-2R (Figure 1A) (Grant et al. 1992; Rickert et al. 2004). Upon binding, the IL-2:IL-2R complex is internalized and IL-2R β and IL-2R γ are degraded in endosomes, while the IL-2R α subunit is recycled to the cell surface (Hémar et al. 1995). Of note, it has been observed that IL-2R α -bound IL-2 is “co-recycled” with this subunit to the cell surface so that IL-2 signaling can be sustained even under low IL-2 concentrations leading to an increased durability of IL-2 signaling. In line with this, IL-2 bound to IL-2R α on the membrane can form an extracellular reservoir which supports sustained, graduated IL-2 signaling (Figure 1B) (Su et al. 2015). Besides high binding affinity, these characteristics add to the increased responsiveness of cells carrying all three receptor subunits, especially under low IL-2 concentrations and enable cells to compete for (limited) IL-2 due to IL-2R α expression (Su et al. 2015). Consequently, differential

Figure 1. Dual role of IL-2 signaling mediated by different IL-2 receptor compositions. (A) Cells expressing the dimeric low-affinity IL-2 receptor (IL-2R) can be activated by high IL-2 doses. On the other hand, low doses of IL-2 can bind to and activate cells expressing all three IL-2R subunits, which form the high-affinity IL-2R. Binding of IL-2 leads to activation of associated Janus family kinases (JAK), leading to phosphorylation of the β and γ receptor subunit and intracellular signaling. (B) IL-2R α alone does not induce intracellular signaling but can function as an extracellular IL-2 reservoir, capturing excess IL-2. MAPK: mitogen-activated protein kinase. PI3K: class I phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase. STAT5: signal transducer and activator of transcription 5. Created with BioRender.com.

expression of the IL-2R subunits results in varying sensitivity to IL-2 of different immune cells. Hereinafter, only some prominent examples for IL-2R⁺ immune cells will be given (namely T- and NK cells). A more detailed summary of IL-2R expression within different organ systems (vasculature, liver, skin) can be found in separate reviews within this issue (Gogesch et al. 2024; Roser et al. 2024; Sommer et al. 2024).

As IL-2 is central in T-cell biology, IL-2R expression on T-cell subsets has been extensively investigated. Unstimulated T_{eff} cells express IL-2R β and IL-2R γ but usually lack IL-2R α , making them unresponsive to low IL-2 concentrations (Siegel and Puri 1991). Similarly, NK cells mainly express the intermediate-affinity dimeric IL-2R (Baume et al. 1992). Upon activation of T- and NK cells by antigens, IL-2, or indirectly, the expression of IL-2R α is enhanced and the trimeric high-affinity IL-2R can be formed (Depper et al. 1985; Kehrl et al. 1988; Baume et al. 1992; Tietze et al. 2012). T_{reg} cells, however, are known to constitutively express the high-affinity receptor (Levings et al. 2001). This mediates their ability to rapidly respond to low amounts of IL-2.

Of the three IL-2R subunits, only IL-2R β and IL-2R γ are known to induce intracellular signaling, mediated by Janus family kinase (JAK) members JAK1 and JAK3 which are bound to IL-2R β and IL-2R γ , respectively (Figure 1(A)) (Miyazaki et al. 1994). Formation of the functional intermediate- or high-affinity IL-2R involves heterodimerization of IL-2R β and IL-2R γ cytoplasmic domains, which induces intracellular signaling (Nakamura et al. 1994). Binding of IL-2 leads to phosphorylation of IL-2R β by JAK1 and JAK3, which can mediate activation of signal transducer and activator of transcription 5 (STAT5) by phosphorylation (Miyazaki et al. 1994; Moriggl et al. 1999;

Bensinger et al. 2004) or activation of Ras. This leads to the induction of the classical mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) cascade resulting in activation of STAT3 (Ng and Cantrell 1997). Furthermore, activation of the Class I phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)-AKT pathway by IL-2 is discussed (Brennan et al. 1997; Ahmed et al. 1997; reviewed by Ross and Cantrell 2018). The complexity of IL-2-induced IL-2R signaling is also depicted in a review within this issue introducing the integration of multi-level information of biological pathways with disease maps using the MINVERA platform (Mazein et al. 2024). In contrast to IL-2R β and IL-2R γ , IL-2R α lacks an intracellular signaling domain so that IL-2 binding to IL-2R α alone does not induce signaling. Rather, cells expressing IL-2R α but lacking the other IL-2R subunits such as dendritic cells, seem to limit IL-2 bioavailability for other cells such as T-cells (Li et al. 2016).

Interestingly, higher sensitivity of T_{reg} cells to IL-2 cannot solely be explained by the increased IL-2R α expression as compared to T_{eff} cells, since differences in intracellular signaling seem to add to this phenomenon. Stimulation of T_{eff} cells by antigen, CD28 co-stimulation, and IL-2 can induce MAPK, PI3K-AKT, and STAT5 signaling pathways, respectively (Bensinger et al. 2004). In T_{reg} cells, on the other hand, high phosphatase and tensin homolog deleted on chromosome 10 (PTEN) expression inhibits PI3K-dependent signaling (Bensinger et al. 2004; Walsh et al. 2006). Thus, IL-2-STAT5 signaling seems to be increased in T_{reg} cells as compared to T_{eff} cells, contributing to the increased IL-2 sensitivity of T_{reg} cells over T_{eff} cells (Yu et al. 2015).

In summary, IL-2R α is central in mediating dual IL-2 responses, as it determines cellular sensitivity toward the

cytokine. Differences in intracellular signaling between T_{reg} cells and T_{eff} cells further determine responses toward different IL-2 concentrations, inducing either immunostimulatory or immunosuppressive effects. These characteristics make recIL-2 an exceptionally interesting molecule for the treatment of both cancer and inflammatory diseases.

RecIL-2 – a therapeutic with severe side effects

Although aldesleukin was a promising anti-cancer immunotherapeutic, severe dose-dependent side effects ranging from cardiovascular, renal, pulmonary, gastrointestinal, endocrinologic, metabolic, neurologic, and hematologic toxicities were described (Siegel and Puri 1991). While aldesleukin-related toxicities can be reversible and most of the patients do not suffer from long-term damage if properly treated (Fyfe et al. 1995; Atkins et al. 1999; Dutcher 2002), the broad range of side effects observed during clinical investigations can lead to the ceasing of the treatment and therefore remains problematic. Common adverse effects of recIL-2 treatment, include chills, fever, hypotension, diarrhea, bilirubinemia, infections, and respiratory and dermatologic complications. Of note, one of the most frequent and dose-limiting adverse effect during Proleukin[®]-immunotherapy is the induction of capillary leakage syndrome, which is linked to further medical complications such as hypotension or reduced organ perfusion. The pathologically-increased vascular permeability leads to an elevated extravasation of protein-rich fluids and immune cells into the underlying tissues, potentially resulting in further organ damage and additional adverse events (Siegel and Puri 1991; Fyfe et al. 1995; Atkins et al. 1999; Rosenberg et al. 1989; Dutcher et al. 2014; FDA/CDER information reference ID: 3165255, 2012; Schwartz et al. 2002; Baluna and Vitetta 1997; Lentsch et al. 1999). Most probably, cytokines secreted by IL-2-activated immune cells lead to secondary activation of endothelial cells, which promotes the development of vascular leakage. So far, the direct effect of IL-2 on different types of endothelial cells is still not fully clarified (Kim et al. 2014; Mier et al. 1989; Damle and Doyle 1989; reviewed in this issue in Gogesch et al. 2024). In addition, several severe side effects of recIL-2 such as sepsis, eosinophilia, and thrombocytopenia are observed in pre-clinical and clinical studies (Harada and Yahara 1993; Klatzmann and Abbas 2015; Wolfgang et al. 1998; Proleukin[®] product information 2024). Experiences over time led to strategies to ameliorate some of the abovementioned side effects. For example, the often-occurring bacterial sepsis during aldesleukin immunotherapy was prevented by establishing a routine antibiotic prophylaxis of patients in later studies (Fyfe et al. 1995; Atkins et al. 1999). Further safety improvement of aldesleukin therapy was achieved by refining patient selection and restricting the administration of aldesleukin to specialized centers (Dutcher et al. 2014). Still, the mechanisms behind the different IL-2-induced systemic and organ-specific toxicities are not fully understood.

Early animal studies found that administration of high human recIL-2 doses to mice or rats reflect toxic effects observed in human patients treated with aldesleukin, including vascular leakage or increased hepatic transaminases, indicative of hepatotoxicity (Rosenstein et al. 1986; Gately et al. 1988; Welbourn et al. 1991; Guan et al. 2012). However, some side effects such as eosinophilia and thrombocytopenia were less severe in mice when compared to the observations in the clinics. Interestingly, in mice, side effects are induced by application of significantly higher doses of human recIL-2. For example, 200 000 IU/

injection, corresponding to roughly 15x the dose used in the clinics, robustly induce vascular leakage (Rosenstein et al. 1986; Gately et al. 1988; Krieg et al. 2010), which could partly be explained by the lower affinity of murine IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ toward human IL-2 (Karakus et al. 2020; Merchant et al. 2022). Some aldesleukin-associated side effects such as skin rashes are not reported in preclinical *in vivo* models or only evolve upon treatment of T- and B-cell-deficient mice applying an IL-2R α -specific recIL-2-antibody construct, suggesting species-specific differences (Roediger et al. 2013). Thus, human-based model systems with increased predictability of recIL-2-induced toxicity came into focus. A model including human microvascular endothelial cells from the lung, for example, was able to indicate increased permeability upon treatment with clinically relevant recIL-2 concentrations or sera from cancer patients receiving high-dose recIL-2 therapy (Kim et al. 2014). These observations highlight that developing new human-based model systems and determining possible key cells or molecules is crucial to understand recIL-2-induced toxicities and to tailor model systems toward improved predictability of side effects. Three adverse outcomes linked to recIL-2 immunotherapy, namely vascular leakage, hepatotoxicity, and skin rash, are in focus of separate reviews published within this issue (Roser et al. 2024; Sommer et al. 2024; Gogesch et al. 2024).

As described, higher doses of recIL-2 aim to activate T_{eff} cells and NK cells, while low doses balance the activation toward a T_{reg} cell response. The dual role of IL-2 makes the cytokine interesting for the treatment of cancers, but also for sc application in low doses. Apparently, in contrast to high-dose recIL-2 therapy, low doses of recIL-2 only induce minor or no side effects and are well tolerated (Schwartz et al. 2002; Saadoun et al. 2011; Hartemann et al. 2013; Humrich et al. 2015; Rosenzweig et al. 2015; Mahmoudpour et al. 2019). Since low doses of recIL-2 facilitate the activation and proliferation of T_{regs} over T_{effs} , it is considered a favorable treatment option for immune-mediated diseases including systemic lupus erythematosus, type I diabetes, psoriasis, or various other autoimmune diseases (Mahmoudpour et al. 2019; reviewed in Lorenzon et al. 2024). However, the therapeutic window of low-dose recIL-2 is narrow and additionally varies from patient to patient, which hinders the identification of safe stimulation of T_{reg} cells without simultaneous activation of other effector cells such as T_{eff} cells or especially NK cells (Yu et al. 2015). Therefore, novel IL-2 molecules with a bias toward T_{reg} cells are an interest of current IL research (summarized in detail below). Moreover, the deeper assessment of patient-related divergences is a desirable approach, because it may pave the way to patient-specific predictions for their individual recIL-2-responsiveness and support determination of optimized or even personalized recIL-2 doses.

Even though aldesleukin was one of the first immunotherapies to be approved and used to treat solid tumors, pathophysiological processes behind side effects, especially occurring upon high-dose recIL-2 therapy, are still not fully understood. Efforts and progress have been made in the past to understand underlying immunological mechanisms. For example, within pre-clinical studies, recIL-2 was shown to induce leukocyte-mediated tissue injury and local secondary effects of chemokines and cytokines such as IL-8, tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , and IL-1 (Lentsch et al. 1999). This suggests that both cytokines and activated immune cells play a critical role in recIL-2-induced pathologies. Analyses to unravel toxicity-related mechanisms and potential biomarkers during recIL-2 therapy are essential to optimize dose selection and the prediction, reduction, or even prevention of pathological outcomes. A better understanding of the mode of

action can improve therapeutic efficacy and safety. Beyond that, novel immunotherapeutic approaches could profit from gained insights.

Bringing new life to recIL-2 therapy – improving safety and specificity

A multitude of novel recIL-2 molecules and therapy regimens were and are currently being investigated. Many of these new recIL-2 compounds aim for a selective responsiveness either toward T_{eff} or T_{reg} cells, for specific application in cancer and autoimmune diseases, respectively. In this section, we aim to provide a snapshot of recently emerging recIL-2 compounds which are more extensively addressed in current reviews as potential therapies (MacDonald et al. 2021; Overwijk et al. 2021). Besides increasing drug bioavailability and improving target tissue- and cell type-specificity, the reduction of treatment-related toxicities is a major concern of these approaches. Common modifications and exemplary drug candidates are described in the following section and summarized in Table 1. An overview of novel recIL-2-based immunotherapies which are tested within clinical trials was recently published as a comprehensive systematic review, summarizing >40 IL-2-based compounds in both anti-cancer-therapies and treatment of autoimmune diseases (Raeyer et al. 2023).

Modifications of the recIL-2 molecule – approaches for new recIL-2 alternatives

One approach for next generation recIL-2 therapy is the modification with polyethylene glycol (PEG) (Ibrahim et al. 2022; Gao et al. 2024). The well-established PEGylation of therapeutics can increase their serum half-life, decrease renal clearance, and protect molecules from enzymatic degradation. Thus, the improved pharmacokinetics potentially enable application of lower doses. Furthermore, by masking the active therapeutic substance, PEGylation can prevent the interaction with immune cells to, e.g., reduce the induction of anti-drug-antibodies, prevent formation of immune complexes, or reduce uptake by mononuclear phagocytes. However, in a substantial part of the population, anti-PEG antibodies can be found, due to daily exposure to PEG-containing products. Of note, anti-PEG antibodies appear not to be associated with pathologies but potentially dampen therapeutic efficacy. However, their exact impact on the safety and efficacy of PEGylated therapeutics remains to be revealed. Although not all PEGylated therapeutics are described to induce immune responses, potential immunogenicity should be considered for each novel drug candidate (Verhoef et al. 2014; Lubich et al. 2016; Gao et al. 2024).

BEMPEG/NKTR-214 (Bempegaldesleukin) is one exemplary PEGylated recIL-2 molecule and a drug candidate for anti-cancer treatment with a selectivity-bias toward the dimeric intermediate-affinity IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ and increased serum half-life compared to recIL-2. In a first-in-human multi-center Phase I study with 28 patients, BEMPEG/NKTR-214 induced tumor shrinkage or stable disease in patients with progressed cancer. The most common adverse events were fatigue, flu-like symptoms, pruritus, rash, decreased appetite, arthralgia, and cough. Six out of 28 patients developed Grade 3 toxicity, and none developed Grade 4 or 5 adverse events, pointing toward a favorable tolerability as compared to aldesleukin (Bentebibel et al. 2019). However, after being tested in several Phase II/III studies as co-treatment with the checkpoint-inhibitor nivolumab, all clinical development of

BEMPEG/NKTR-214 was announced to be discontinued in 2022 due to unmet criteria (Bristol Myers Squibb Press Release 2022, as of 28.02.2024).

Since uncontrolled PEGylation is concerned to impair the fine-tuning of novel molecules and lead to heterogeneous products (Zhang et al. 2021), site-specific PEGylation using a copper-free click reaction has been applied by Zhang et al. (2021) to generate dual-31/51-20K. This T_{reg} cell-biased recIL-2 alternative preferentially binds to IL-2R α , which could potentially be a drug candidate for the treatment of autoimmune diseases. For this molecule, an enhanced therapeutic efficacy in mouse models of lupus, collagen-induced arthritis, and graft-versus-host disease and a low risk of undesired immunogenicity was evaluated by injection of dual-31/51-20K in mice and consequent determination of antibodies against PEG moieties (Zhang et al. 2021).

As a further approach, mutated recIL-2 molecules (muteins) have been investigated for several years to direct the binding affinity toward specific IL-2R subunits (Rosalia et al. 2014). THOR-707 is a mutated recIL-2 molecule which is site-specifically PEGylated and harbors enhanced intermediate-affinity IL-2R $\beta\gamma$ engagement and reduced affinity for IL-2R α . Compared to aldesleukin, single doses of THOR-707 given to mice exhibited a favorable bioavailability and CD8⁺ T- and NK cell expansion with concomitant reduced plasma IL-5 levels, suggesting ameliorated pathologies such as vascular leakage (MacDonald et al. 2021) and peripheral eosinophilia (van Gool et al. 2014). In a murine melanoma model, THOR-707 elicited anti-tumor activity and increased CD8⁺ T- and NK cell but not T_{reg} cell infiltration in tumors (Ptacin et al. 2021), highlighting the specificity of the recIL-2 mutein to the intermediate-affinity IL-2R. Currently, clinical Phase I and II studies are recruiting patients to study the safety and activity of THOR-707 alone or in combination with other treatment protocols in patients with advanced cancers of different entities (ClinicalTrials.gov identifiers e.g.: NCT04009681; NCT05104567). Preliminary results indicate increased CD8⁺ T- and NK cell numbers, while eosinophilia or vascular leakage were not observed (Sanofi Press 2021). However, other organ toxicities such as skin rashes, increased hepatotoxicity markers, or renal injury might occur (Janku et al. 2021).

Another approach is to modify the specificity of IL-2 by generating recIL-2 fusion proteins. ALKS-4230 (Nemvaleukin Alfa) is a recIL-2 mutein fused to the extracellular portion of the IL-2R α without impeding the interaction of recIL-2 with the intermediate-affinity IL-2R for preferential activity on CD8⁺ T- and NK cells during cancer immunotherapy. In phosphoflow experiments measuring cellular activation *via* STAT5 phosphorylation in human peripheral blood mononuclear cells, ALKS-4230 had a comparable potency toward CD8⁺ T- and NK cells, but a decreased EC₅₀ value in T_{reg} cells when compared to recIL-2. The efficacy of ALKS-4230 was confirmed in a murine melanoma lung colonialization model in which a dose response of up to 100% inhibition of tumor growth was measured. Furthermore, it was shown that either *iv* or *sc* administration elicits anti-tumor activity (Lopes et al. 2020). Among others, the safety and tolerability of ALKS-4230 is assessed in ongoing and currently recruiting clinical Phase I, II, and III studies as monotherapy and in combination with pembrolizumab (an immune checkpoint inhibitor) in patients with advanced solid tumors and was reported to be generally well tolerated (ClinicalTrials.gov identifier e.g., NCT04144517, NCT05092360; Vaishampayan et al. 2022; Winer et al. 2022). In a completed Phase I/II study, treating advanced solid tumors, ALKS-4230 monotherapy

Table 1. Overview of possible IL-2 modifications aiming to improve safety and efficacy of recIL-2 therapy including examples and ongoing clinical trials. Molecules modified using different strategies are listed in multiple categories. Icons created with BioRender.com.

	Modification of IL-2	Possible advantages	Examples	Application; clinical phase (Reference)
	PEGylation	Increased serum half-life and stability; reduced immunogenicity	BEMPEG/NKTR-214 (Bempegaldesleukin)	Anti-cancer-treatment; progressed to clinical trial Phase III in combination with checkpoint inhibitor (e.g. NCT03729245, NCT04410445); clinical development terminated
			THOR-707	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase I/II (e.g. NCT04009681, NCT05104567)
			dual-31/51-20K	Autoimmune diseases; pre-clinics (Zhang et al. 2021)
	Glycosylation	Increased serum half-life and stability, ameliorated tolerability, targeted binding to specific IL-2R subtypes	NCR2/NKp44	Autoimmune diseases; pre-clinics (Ottolenghi et al. 2021)
	Fusion proteins	Increased serum half-life and tolerability, targeted delivery and binding to specific IL-2R subtypes, fine-tuned biological activity (e.g. pro-drugs)	ALKS-4230	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial Phase I, II, and III (e.g. NCT02799095, NCT04144517, NCT05092360, and Vaishampayan et al. 2022)
XTX202			Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase I/II (NCT05052268)	
Darleukin/Daromun			Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase II/III (NCT02938299 and NCT03567889, Daromun), clinical trial phases I/II Darleukin in combination with other drugs (NCT02086721, NCT02957019, NCT01055522)	
	Muteins	Targeted binding to specific IL-2R subtypes, introducing mutations that serve as binding sites for other modification (e.g. PEGylation sites, linkers for fusion proteins)	THOR-707	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase I/II (e.g. NCT04009681, NCT05104567)
			ALKS-4230	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial Phase I, II, and III (e.g. NCT02799095, NCT04144517, NCT05092360, and Vaishampayan et al. 2022)
			XTX202	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase I/II (NCT05052268)
			Darleukin/Daromun	Anti-cancer-treatment; clinical trial phase II/III (NCT02938299) and NCT03567889, Daromun), clinical trial phases I/II Darleukin in combination with other drugs (NCT02086721, NCT02957019, NCT01055522)
	Delivery systems	Targeted drug delivery and controlled drug release, increased anti-tumor activity	Ad5/3-E2F-d24-vIL2)	Anti-cancer-treatment; pre-clinics (Quixabeira et al. 2021)

induced robust expansion of CD8⁺ T- and NK cells, with limited effect on T_{reg} cells. Both mono- and combination therapy with pembrolizumab produced responses in several tumor entities. The most frequent treatment-related adverse event of Grade 3/4 were anemia, neutropenia, and decreased neutrophils (Vaishampayan et al. 2022; NCT02799095).

Furthermore, Ottolenghi et al. describe S2A, a recIL-2 molecule, which is flanked by highly glycosylated hinge regions derived from the natural cytotoxicity triggering receptor 2 (NCR2/NKp44) (Ottolenghi et al. 2021). Glycosylation is the covalent attachment of glycans to proteins, which can influence their pharmacodynamics and -kinetics (Solá and Griebenow

2010), aiming to increase serum half-life of the new recIL-2 compound. S2A showed a bias toward anti-inflammatory reactions in murine *in vivo* experiments as it promoted T_{reg} cell proliferation while retaining CD8⁺ T cell numbers, which could be beneficial for the treatment of autoimmune diseases. The authors hypothesize that structural changes due to the NCR2 hinge fusion might explain the altered binding affinity. Compared to recIL-2-treated mice, S2A-treated animals exhibited less vascular leakage in lungs, which points toward a favorable tolerability of this novel recIL-2 molecule (Ottolenghi et al. 2021). No information about clinical trials for S2A could be identified.

ProIL2, a cytokine-receptor-masked prodrug for recIL-2, is another approach combining several modification strategies to enable a targeted anti-tumor and a CD8⁺ T-cell-specific treatment. ProIL2 consists of two human Fc domains: one is linked to a recIL-2 mutein with a GGGGS linker and the other to the IL-2R β subunit with a matrix metalloproteinase (MMP)-cleavable linker. In its uncleaved form, the IL-2R β moiety blocks the IL-2 activity. At the tumor site, however, MMPs expressed by tumor cells cleave the IL-2R β from ProIL2, leading to the active form, SumIL2-Fc, a mutein with a bias toward CD8⁺ T-cells. ProIL2 cleavage was assessed by injection in tumor-bearing mice. Quantification of the uncleaved (inactive) and cleaved (active) amount of ProIL2 in tumors, liver, lung, and spleen showed that within the tumor, significantly higher levels of the inactive ProIL2 could be found when compared to peripheral organs. Additionally, more than 50% of ProIL2 was cleaved into the active form SumIL-2-Fc in tumors, while in the peripheral organs it was less than 25%. This indicates that ProIL2 preferentially localizes to tumors where it is cleaved into its active form. Both injection of SumIL-2-Fc and ProIL2 exerted similar antitumor effects, while ProIL2 mediated less toxicity, as indicated by reduced serum inflammatory markers. This presumably translates to a broader therapeutic window of ProIL2. In immune checkpoint blockade-resistant tumors in mice, administration of anti-PD-L1 or ProIL2 alone was ineffective, while combination treatment with ProIL2 and anti-PD-L1 was able to overcome resistance and led to tumor control. While peripheral toxicity of ProIL2 was reduced in comparison to SumIL-2-Fc, low levels of tissue inflammation were observed in murine lungs and livers, possibly due to the presence of MMP from neutrophils and macrophages, activating the ProIL-2 in these tissues (Hsu et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2023). Currently, a prodrug with a comparable mechanism (XTX202) is analyzed regarding safety and tolerability in a first-in-human Phase I/II clinical trial for therapeutic efficacy of advanced solid tumors (NCT05052268).

Modifications of recIL-2 delivery

Besides targeting the molecule itself, another way to alter pharmacologic properties of recIL-2 is to modify delivery, e.g. by employing nanoparticles. For instance, nanoparticle-encapsulated recIL-2 for ameliorated drug delivery and a controlled drug release or nanoparticles coated with anti-recIL-2 monoclonal antibodies for neutralization and cellular targeting are some of the approaches recently reviewed (Raker et al. 2020).

An example for a recIL-2 fusion protein for targeted delivery is L19-IL2 (Darleukin), a recIL-2 molecule fused to the monoclonal antibody L19. L19 binds to the alternatively spliced extradomain B of fibronectin, a marker of newly formed blood vessels during tumor angiogenesis that is rarely present in healthy adult tissues. The aim is to inject a recIL-2 molecule targeting vascularized tumors with shorter and fewer administrations while

simultaneously increasing efficacy compared to intralesional injection of untargeted molecules. Thus, this approach targets to limit treatment-related adverse events. A phase II clinical trial consisting of a combined L19-IL2 and L19-TNF treatment, i.e., a treatment approach, which involves two antibody-cytokine fusions as active moieties (called Daromun), was conducted in patients with advanced stage melanoma and showed promising anti-tumor effects. There were no serious adverse events reported and the most common side effects were minor, including swelling, erythema, pain at the site of injection, fever, and headache (Danielli et al. 2015). L19-IL2/L19-TNF (Daromun) will be assessed in melanoma patients (ClinicalTrials.gov identifiers: NCT02938299 and NCT03567889). Further studies are ongoing testing L19-IL2 (Darleukin) in combination with other drugs or radiotherapy (ClinicalTrials.gov identifiers e.g.: NCT02086721; van Limbergen et al. 2021).

In addition, oncolytic adenoviruses have been shown to be applicable for the targeted delivery of cytokines to tumors (Ranki et al. 2016). Quixabeira et al. (2021) constructed an adenovirus coding for a recIL-2 variant (Ad5/3-E2F-d24-vIL2), aiming to promote cytotoxic T-cell-mediated anti-tumor response. *In vivo* experiments with tumor-bearing Syrian golden hamsters attributed a superior anti-tumor response of vIL-2-armed oncolytic adenovirus-treated animals when compared to the recIL-2-armed virus or mock control-treated group. Analysis of the mechanism of action suggests that vIL-2 treatment induces CD8⁺ T-cell efficiency and ameliorates major histocompatibility complex (MHC) II tumor antigen presentation, thus leading to a high anti-tumor activity (Quixabeira et al. 2021). For both nanoparticle- and oncolytic adenovirus-mediated IL-2 delivery, clinical trials are outstanding and will likely contribute to the revival of recIL-2 as an immunotherapy.

Concluding remarks

The discovery of IL-2 as an immunomodulating therapeutic with the potential to target distinct immune cell types can be seen as a major breakthrough in the field of immunotherapies. As a drawback, however, several severe toxicities limited the use of high-dose aldesleukin for the treatment of cancers. Nevertheless, the dual role of recIL-2 either inducing immunostimulatory or immunosuppressive effects still makes it an attractive drug for the treatment of various immune-related diseases. The molecules and approaches to modify recIL-2 that we summarized here are examples of recent approaches described in current literature. Further approaches are under investigation, highlighting that recIL-2 still is a molecule of high interest, which is further supported by the application of these novel constructs within clinical trials. It is clear that there will be no one-fits-all new recIL-2 compound suitable for all indications. Instead, with these modifications and their combinations, the mode of action can be directed into one of the dual directions. This additionally enables the customization of novel compounds for specific pathologies and the limitation of off-target effects. Regarding this, it is necessary to carefully address the pharmacodynamics, -kinetics, and the toxicities of these new recIL-2 compounds. For this purpose, immune-related adverse outcome pathways (irAOP) were developed for recIL-2-mediated toxicities as a use case. Exemplary irAOP for recIL-2-induced vascular leak syndrome, hepatotoxicity, and skin rash are described in detail within this issue (Gogesch et al. 2024; Roser et al. 2024; Sommer et al. 2024). Further development of these irAOP within imSAVAR shall result in an in-depth picture to be used as a basis for pre-clinical

safety assessment of other new IL-2-based therapies, which are currently being tested or developed. Finally, the identification of biomarkers to predict adverse effects of IL-2-based immunotherapy aims to help alleviate toxic effects, therefore improving overall patient well-being.

Declaration of interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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